

CLINICAL DYNAMICS OF DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS THAT OCCUR AFTER MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Conclusion: The article presents the clinical and dynamic characteristics of depressive syndromes that occur after myocardial infarction. It turns out that etiologically, depressions that occur in the first months after myocardial infarction can be associated with nosogenia, and after six months with somatogenia.

Keywords: Myocardial infarction, depressive syndrome, clinical and dynamic characteristics, etiological aspects, somatogeny.

Introduction. Relevance of the problem. Depression is often similar to other, somatic, diseases, and in such cases diseases of two different areas - mental and somatic - exacerbate each other, sometimes with serious consequences. The combined depression rate among cardiovascular patients is 22-33%. 17-27% of patients with coronary artery disease who undergo a coronary angiography procedure are diagnosed with depression, and depression in the post-infarction period is diagnosed in 16-45% of cases [1-3]. The presence of depression in patients with cardiovascular diseases not only complicates the course and therapy of these diseases, but also reduces the life expectancy of patients. It is clear and predicted that the most pronounced emotional disturbances are observed in patients with myocardial infarction, since even with satisfactory well-being, the diagnosis of myocardial infarction is associated with a threat to life for a person. In addition to worrying health concerns, dark thoughts about the future, depression, fear of possible disability, anxious thoughts about the well-being of the family arise. Without proper intervention, these disorders persist for a year in 25% of survivors. According to other data, mental disorders were reported in 28% of cases. In 50% of patients, an increase in neurotic characteristics was observed [4-7].

Myocardial infarction is one of the most severe forms of coronary artery disease (CAD) and is one of the main causes of death in patients with cardiovascular disease [8]. In acute myocardial infarction (ami), many factors affect development, course, occurrence of complications and prognosis. In recent decades, there has been sufficient data showing that AMI-related depressive disorders negatively affect the clinical course of the post-infarction period, the functional state of patients, and their quality of life [9]. However, an analysis of a number of major epidemiological studies has shown that the presence of depression is associated with an increased risk of myocardial infarction and cardiovascular death [10]. The results of an eight-year epidemiological study conducted on the basis of The Who program "Monica" showed that the risk of developing myocardial infarction is associated with depression [11], as well as depression was found to be

a prognostic factor of death within 6-18 months after AMI [12]. Thus, AMI depression has independent prognostic significance in relation to mortality [13]. The prevalence of depressive states in patients with cardiovascular disease ranges from 18 to 60% [14], which is much higher than in other forms of somatic pathology and significantly exceeds the prevalence of depressions in the population [15]. Barefoot J. C., Schroll M. (1996) found that people with depression have a risk of developing CAD and almost 2 times higher than those without depression [16]. According to the World Health Organization, as of 2020, depression is second only to CAD in terms of years of total life reduction due to disability [17], which explains the great interest of professionals in the problem of Affective Disorders and CAD comorbidity [18]. Currently, the relationship between anxiety disorders and AMI is much less studied than depression and AMI. The prevalence of anxiety disorders in patients with AMI, according to various estimates, ranges from 16,7 to 59,5% [19]. According to some authors, the presence of anxiety increased the likelihood of developing cardiovascular complications [20]. Thus, it becomes clear the need for an early diagnosis of anxiety-depressive disorders in Cardiological patients, in particular in patients with AMI. The main methods of diagnosing depression are careful collection of complaints and history, physical examination of the patient, manifestation of any signs of depression and anxiety in the process, assessment of mental state using a special test [21]. Depression is a mental disorder characterized by a negative mood, pessimistic self-assessment, surrounding persistence, and pathologically diminished mood (hypothymia) with status in the future. Depressive mood swings, along with impaired cognitive processes, are accompanied by motor inhibition, decreased activity motifs, somato-vegetative dysfunctions [22]. In accordance with the MBK-10 [23] criteria, the classification of mental and behavioral disorders (World Health Organization, DSM-IV) [24], a number of key and additional characters of a depressive episode are distinguished. Di AgNOz de pres SIV is set when the episode maintains the shows for 2 weeks or more [25].

According to the ICD 10 and DSM IV classifications, the following forms of anxiety disorders are distinguished: severe stress response and adaptation disorders, phobic disorders, panic disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder (obsessive neurosis), general anxiety disorders and mixed anxiety-depressive disorders. There are two main groups of symptoms characteristic of anxiety syndromes: psychic, defined by the nature of anxiety formation and flow, and somatic, associated with activation of the autonomic nervous system [26-30]. Anxiety is a feeling of anxiety, irritability, anticipating problems, internal tension for no apparent reason. Anxiety disorders almost always involve autonomic symptoms—for example, palpitations (sinus tachycardia), a feeling of heart failure, extrasystole, cardialgia, clearly associated with breathing movement, unstable blood pressure level (rise or fall), a feeling of heat (hot flashes) or tremors, shortness of breath, nausea, feeling of air, difficulty breathing, dysphagia ("lump in the throat"), headache, dizziness, abdominal pain and discomfort, unstable stool. Vegetative symptomatology is polysystemic in nature [31]. The above disorders exist most days of the week and for at least 6 months. The diagnosis is made in the presence of the main symptom, in combination with the above three or more criteria. For the diagnosis of anxiety-depressive spectrum disorders, special scales are widely used that allow you to identify depression in the early stages of its development, the most common of which are:

The purpose of the study is to study the clinical and dynamic characteristics of depressive states that occur after myocardial infarction.

Materials and research methods. A study of 341 patients diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction was conducted. The materials of the Russian conference with patient-international participation are divided into 2 groups. Comprising 233 patients with the first, primary, acute myocardial infarction, they developed depressive disorders that were later confirmed using a clinical and diagnostic scale; the second group comprised 108 patients who also experienced acute myocardial infarction but did not suffer from symptoms of depression afterwards. In the post-infarction period, clinical and dynamic monitoring of patients with situational control was carried out a month, three months, six months, 12 months after

myocardial infarction. A clinical follow-up method was used to determine the presence of symptoms of depression (the patient was diagnosed with "acute myocardial infarction" from the first hour after hospitalization), as well as the Hamilton and Montgomery-Asberg scales for the first three days in hospital. If depressive symptoms are not detected on the first day after an ischemic attack, then for diagnostic purposes, the scales were used daily until clinically significant symptoms of depression of any severity were identified, after discharge from the hospital – three months, six months, 12 months later. myocardial infarction (mi); After determining the presence of depressive disorder, the use of scales was carried out within the above deadlines. If symptoms of depression are not detected for 3 months after an ischemic attack, patients are not included in the main group of the study.

According to ICD-10, a clinically significant depressive disorder consists of the following symptoms: the main ones – a) a decrease in mood almost every day and most of the day, as well as in relation to the specific norm of the patient, regardless of the situation; b) a decrease in interest (loss) and the ability to enjoy activities usually associated with positive emotions; ; b) changes in appetite (decreased or increased) with corresponding changes in body weight; C) repetitive thoughts of death, suicide or self-harm; d) a dark and pessimistic view of the future; e) ideas of guilt and self-deprecation; f) A feeling of self-esteem and self-confidence; g) decreased concentration, inability to concentrate, decreased ability to think, hesitation or hesitation in decision making. Mild depression (F 32.0 on ICD-10) is characterized by the presence of two main and two additional symptoms. Moderate depression (F 32.1 on ICD-10) is characterized by the presence of two major and three to four additional symptoms. Severe depression (F 32.2 or F 32.3 in ICD-10) is characterized by the presence of three major, four or more additional symptoms, some of which are significantly manifested.

Research results. Among patients with DS, in the early days following them, more than half (51,1%) of them recorded a steady decrease in mood than other symptom materials, viz. these patients showed an affective component of depression, while the ideator component of depression manifested to one degree or another in inhibition of thinking, with motor inhibition (motor component) found in 21,5% of patients observed in 27,5%. In patients with almost the same frequency, a type of alarming and melancholic effect (47,0% and 41,2%, respectively) was recorded, the type of dysphoric effect occurs in 11,8% of cases, which is 3,5 times less than the alarming and melancholic type.

In accordance with the research tasks, one month, three, six and twelve months after myocardial infarction, the condition of the patients was analyzed. The same analysis was carried out in patients in the control group. It turned out that 1 month after them, only patients in the control group did not have depressive disorders, depressive syndromes were recorded in the main group of patients. Clinically, 43,8 percent of patients reported asthenic depression, 32,2 percent reported DS anxiety depression, 13,7 percent reported melancholic depression, and 10,3 percent reported dysphoric depression. A significant change in the DS clinical vector towards asthenic exacerbation and a decrease in melancholic and anxiety depressions is associated with an improvement in the somatic state of specific patients and, in connection with this, an adequate attitude towards their condition and diseases. This is confirmed by patient examination data three months after he experienced it.

In the main group, the decrease in symptoms in patients with melancholic and dysphoric depression is significant, but the number of patients with anxious depressive disorders is increasing. Interestingly, after 3 months in the control group, 18 patients (16,7%) were diagnosed with anxiety depression. Such a change was associated with the need for certain restrictions in the patient's life: compliance with the regime of work and rest and the regime of therapy, refusal of the usual lifestyle and bad habits (smoking, alcohol), hyperopia of relatives for the patient, reassessment of their social roles. Attention should be paid to this group of patients with a clinical expression of depression: sleep disorders, superficial sleep, a feeling of fear of repetition by him, constant ideas to blame himself for the wrong behavior that led to them, episodes

of vegetative paroxysm with a pronounced heartbeat, a feeling of lack of air, unpleasant sensations in the heart area, patients were mistaken for the next person., they called an ambulance, believed that they were being examined by incompetent specialists, argued with doctors and relatives. However, according to the measurements of Hamilton and Montgomery-Asberg, this DS was assessed as mild depression, which required more psychotherapeutic intervention in the form of convincing patients that there were no im symptoms and sleep correction.

6 months after them, the number of non-dr patients increased significantly. With a significant decrease in patients with anxiety and asthenic depression, patients with a hypochondriac variant of DS appeared, which was characterized by constant search for their symptoms, frequent measurements of heart rate and blood pressure, going to cardiologists and therapists, frequent changes in doctors and distrust of consultations. In addition, the attitude of these patients towards others changed, they demanded the attention of relatives and tried to show everyone how seriously they were sick, almost stopped working and were passive to family problems. In the control group, the number of patients with anxiety depression decreased by 2 times.

A year after he experienced it, a slightly different picture was observed. Among patients studied, 7,3% of the core group and 0,9% of the control group maintained symptoms of depression. Anxiety and hypochondriac depressions have been reported in the main group among DS. In terms of violence, these depressions have been described as mild. The awareness of the presence of a serious disease, the fear of repeating it, the inability to internally change the attitude towards something in the past, the lack of objective information about the disease and its consequences provides the basis for maintaining an internal psychological balance, which disrupts the patient's emotional response, as a result of which depressive disorders remain. Obviously, this group of patients requires the attention of cardiologists and psychiatrists when developing a psychocorrectional reward plan.

Discussion. In prolonged cases of depression, the severity of Affective Disorders was often directly related to the severity of the somatic condition. If such non-protracted depressive episodes were mainly associated with "specific views of the disease", the severity of their symptoms depended on the interview with the doctor and the information received from him, the level of awareness of their diagnosis, possible complications, and were not at all at all dependent. the general somatic condition, then the course of long-term depression in patients, worsened with Cardiological heaviness. and the general somatic condition of patients. In most cases of long-term depression, psychosomatic parallelism was manifested by a generalization of asthenic symptom complexes (in combination with increased general weakness, intolerance to loads, lethargy, adinamia, daytime insomnia, early insomnia) with a worsening of somatic condition. At the same time, it was noted that long-lasting depressions always recorded to a certain extent specific cognitive distortions (decreased memory for past events, limited ability to understand what is happening around, remembering new information, impaired concentration).

In the first place with short depressive episodes appeared depression, pessimistic perception of the disease, hypertrophied assessment of its consequences, anxiety about the repeated attack of angina pectoris, fear of death, impending disability. Increased self-observation with the recording of the smallest changes in well-being is sometimes combined with many complaints that do not have a sufficient somatic basis. Other components of depressive disorder include hystero-conversion (lump in the throat, tremor, "claw"-shaped limb drowsiness), somatic-vegetative (tachycardia, dyspnea, insomnia), and asthenic (increased fatigue, decreased activity, complaints of weakness, loss of activity.) symptom complexes.

The reverse development of such depressions coincided with a period of stabilization of the manifestation of somatic disease, when the risk of death was minimized, physical activity began to recover, and the level of anxiety decreased.

The above suggests that the duration of a depressive episode after acute myocardial infarction may indicate the origin of this symptom complex. Thus, depressive episodes lasting up to six months can be attributed to nosogenia, that is, to cases in which the psyche has a response to a traumatic situation, in our case to severe somatic disease. Long-lasting depressive episodes can probably be associated with somatogenesis with a high degree of confidence, i.e. cases that are pathophysiologically related to severe pathology of internal organs, i.e. in patients with more severe forms of cardiac pathology, the decrease in depression occurs at a slower pace.

Conclusions.

1. The majority of patients with acute myocardial infarction experience a moderate (moderate) depressive episode upon primary diagnosis (71,6% on the Hamilton Scale and 72,7% on the Montgomery-Asberg scale);
2. The identification of depressive symptoms within a year of experiencing it determines the need to study a set of factors that lead to the formation of depressive disorders in patients who experience it, even in patients in the control group.
3. Post-infarction depressive episodes lasting up to six months can be associated with nosogenia; depressive episodes of post-prolonged infarction Genesis may possibly be associated with somatogenesis with high confidence.

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